

Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares: Orders 44 to 47

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The work is also available at author's site:
<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19786>

Abstract

*This work bring different ways of representing prime magic squares. These are of types: **blocks**, **block-bordered**, **concentric**, **nested**, etc. This work is for the orders 44 to 47. For prime magic squares of orders 6 to 43 refer author's work [10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15]. In case of prime magic squares of orders 47, the compositions of order 45 are applied over 47 considering **single-layer border** representing as **block-bordered prime magic squares**, with internal blocks based on different compositions of prime magic squares of order 46. Even though the magic square of order 46 is not prime but there is only one way to represent in blocks, i.e., multiples of 23. Due to this we considered more examples using compositions of prime magic square of order 44 as internal block.*

Keywords: magic squares, prime magic squares, block-wise magic squares, concentric magic squares, recreational mathematics.

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1 Introduction

During past years, the author studied block-wise constructions of magic squares. The work for the magic square of orders 8 to 47. Below are few examples:

1.1 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 8

Let's consider a **pandiagonal** of order 8 is given by

8x8	pan	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260
260	7	60	1	62	15	52	9	54	260	
260	2	61	8	59	10	53	16	51	260	
260	64	3	58	5	56	11	50	13	260	
260	57	6	63	4	49	14	55	12	260	
260	23	44	17	46	31	36	25	38	260	
260	18	45	24	43	26	37	32	35	260	
260	48	19	42	21	40	27	34	29	260	
	41	22	47	20	33	30	39	28	260	
	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

It is composed four **equal sums pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4.

1.2 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 9

Let's consider a **pandiagonal** magic square of order 9 is given by

9x9 pan	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	
369	22	71	30	27	64	32	20	69	34	369
369	35	21	67	28	23	72	33	25	65	369
369	66	31	26	68	36	19	70	29	24	369
369	40	8	75	45	1	77	38	6	79	369
369	80	39	4	73	41	9	78	43	2	369
369	3	76	44	5	81	37	7	74	42	369
369	58	53	12	63	46	14	56	51	16	369
369	17	57	49	10	59	54	15	61	47	369
	48	13	62	50	18	55	52	11	60	369
	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

In this case, blocks of order 3 are **semi-magic squares** (sum of only rows and columns) with equal magic sums.

Below is another example, where blocks of order 3 are magic squares, but the magic square of order 9 is not **pandiagonal**:

9 mgc										369
	31	36	29	76	81	74	13	18	11	369
	30	32	34	75	77	79	12	14	16	369
	35	28	33	80	73	78	17	10	15	369
	22	27	20	40	45	38	58	63	56	369
	21	23	25	39	41	43	57	59	61	369
	26	19	24	44	37	42	62	55	60	369
	67	72	65	4	9	2	49	54	47	369
	66	68	70	3	5	7	48	50	52	369
	71	64	69	8	1	6	53	46	51	369
	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369	369

In this case, blocks of order 3 are magic squares with **different magic sums**.

1.3 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 10

Let's consider a magic square of order 10 with inner part as magic square of order 8 with blocks of order 4 is given by

10x10	mgc											505
	91	86	16	84	18	14	4	98	2	92	505	
	13	47	58	19	78	39	66	27	70	88	505	
	89	22	75	50	55	30	67	42	63	12	505	
	11	82	23	54	43	74	31	62	35	90	505	
	96	51	46	79	26	59	38	71	34	5	505	
	1	48	57	20	77	40	65	28	69	100	505	
	93	21	76	49	56	29	68	41	64	8	505	
	7	81	24	53	44	73	32	61	36	94	505	
	95	52	45	80	25	60	37	72	33	6	505	
	9	15	85	17	83	87	97	3	99	10	505	
	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	

The blocks of order 8 are **equal sums pandiagonal** magic squares of order 10.

1.4 Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Order 11

The **block-bordered** magic square of order 11 with inner part as magic square of order 9 is given by

11x11	mgc											671
	12	20	18	16	14	113	114	116	118	120	10	671
	121	21	38	43	55	60	68	80	85	99	1	671
	119	53	58	72	75	92	97	28	33	41	3	671
	117	82	87	95	26	31	45	48	65	70	5	671
	115	47	25	30	69	50	64	94	81	89	7	671
	11	67	54	62	101	79	84	42	23	37	111	671
	13	96	77	91	40	27	35	74	52	57	109	671
	15	34	39	29	59	73	51	90	98	76	107	671
	17	63	71	49	88	93	83	32	46	24	105	671
	19	86	100	78	36	44	22	61	66	56	103	671
	112	102	104	106	108	9	8	6	4	2	110	671
	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671	671

The blocks of order 8 are **equal sums pandiagonal** magic squares of order 10.

1.5 Block-Wise Magic Squares of Order 12

Below are three different ways of writing **block-wise** magic squares of order 12. First as magic square formed by 16 blocks of magic squares of order 3 with different magic sums. Second as magic square formed by 9 blocks of **pandiagonal** magic squares of order 4 with equal magic sums. Third as 4 blocks of order 6 with equal magic sums. In the first two cases, the magic square of order 12 is **pandiagonal**, while third case, it is just a magic square.

• Blocks of Order 3

12x12	pan	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
870	98	1	51	72	22	119	78	28	125	140	43	93	870
870	3	50	97	118	71	24	124	77	30	45	92	139	870
870	49	99	2	23	120	70	29	126	76	91	141	44	870
870	131	34	84	87	37	134	57	7	104	113	16	66	870
870	36	83	130	133	86	39	103	56	9	18	65	112	870
870	82	132	35	38	135	85	8	105	55	64	114	17	870
870	67	117	20	5	102	52	47	144	94	73	123	26	870
870	21	68	115	100	53	6	142	95	48	27	74	121	870
870	116	19	69	54	4	101	96	46	143	122	25	75	870
870	88	138	41	32	129	79	14	111	61	58	108	11	870
870	42	89	136	127	80	33	109	62	15	12	59	106	870
	137	40	90	81	31	128	63	13	110	107	10	60	870
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

• **Blocks of Order 4**

12x12	pan	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870
870	7	140	1	142	15	132	9	134	23	124	17	126	870	
870	2	141	8	139	10	133	16	131	18	125	24	123	870	
870	144	3	138	5	136	11	130	13	128	19	122	21	870	
870	137	6	143	4	129	14	135	12	121	22	127	20	870	
870	31	116	25	118	39	108	33	110	47	100	41	102	870	
870	26	117	32	115	34	109	40	107	42	101	48	99	870	
870	120	27	114	29	112	35	106	37	104	43	98	45	870	
870	113	30	119	28	105	38	111	36	97	46	103	44	870	
870	55	92	49	94	63	84	57	86	71	76	65	78	870	
870	50	93	56	91	58	85	64	83	66	77	72	75	870	
870	96	51	90	53	88	59	82	61	80	67	74	69	870	
	89	54	95	52	81	62	87	60	73	70	79	68	870	
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	

• **Blocks of Order 6**

12	mgc													870
	1	143	142	141	2	6	19	125	124	123	20	24	870	
	138	8	136	9	11	133	120	26	118	27	29	115	870	
	132	131	15	16	128	13	114	113	33	34	110	31	870	
	18	14	129	130	17	127	36	32	111	112	35	109	870	
	7	134	10	135	137	12	25	116	28	117	119	30	870	
	139	5	3	4	140	144	121	23	21	22	122	126	870	
	55	89	88	87	56	60	37	107	106	105	38	42	870	
	84	62	82	63	65	79	102	44	100	45	47	97	870	
	78	77	69	70	74	67	96	95	51	52	92	49	870	
	72	68	75	76	71	73	54	50	93	94	53	91	870	
	61	80	64	81	83	66	43	98	46	99	101	48	870	
	85	59	57	58	86	90	103	41	39	40	104	108	870	
	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	

More on these kind of magic squares can be seen in author’s work [29, 30, 31]. The aim of this work write magic squares with blocks of order 4 with distinct prime number entries.

Based on the idea of blocks, block-borders, etc. given above,we shall concentrate our work in this direction on **prime magic squares**. This whole work is given in many parts.

2 Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares of Orders 44 to 47

This work brings different ways representing magic squares in prime numbers. Initial aim is represent in terms of blocks. Some of possibilities led us to concentric or single-layer bordered magic squares. It includes blocks of orders 3, 4, 5, etc. Sometimes these blocks are of **equal** or **different** magic sums. This work is for the orders 39 to 43. For the previous orders refer authors work [10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15]. Also there are two more works on prime magic squares recently done by the author. The first one is on **concentric single-layer bordered prime magic squares** of orders 120 and 121 [8]. The second one is **block-structured** prime magic squares of order 1220 multiples of 4 [9].

Whenever, we write **prime magic square**, it means that the magic squares are composed of **distinct prime number entries**, except in few cases, where the central constant 1000003 is repeating. It is considered only in case of odd order primes magic squares, where we need the **equal sums** magic squares.

This work is for the **prime magic squares** of orders 44 to 47. The table below give different representations studied in this work:

Order	Representations
44	11 (01-11)
45	11 (12-22)
46	04 (23-26)
47	06 (27-32)
Total	32

2.1 Prime Magic Squares of Order 44

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 44 with different representations. We know that $44 := 4 \times 11$. It means that most of the blocks are composition of prime magic squares of orders 4, 11 and 22.

Example 1. Different Sums Blocks of Order 4. Let’s consider following **prime magic square** of order 44:

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 44. It is composed of **equal sums** prime magic squares of order 4.

Example 3. Different Sums Blocks of Order 11. Let's consider following **prime magic square** of order 44:

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 44. It is composed of different **equal sums** concentric prime magic squares of order 11.

Example 5. Different Sums Blocks of Order 11. Let's consider following **prime magic square** of order 44:

A 44x44 grid of numbers, representing a prime magic square. The numbers are arranged in a block-structured pattern, where each row and column contains a sequence of numbers that likely sum to a constant value.

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 44. It is composed of **different sums prime magic squares** of order 11. These primes magic squares are nested with **different sums prime magic squares** of order 3 making prime magic squares of order 9.

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 44. It is composed of **equal sums** prime magic squares of order 22. Each block of order 22 is nested with prime magic square of order 20. It is further composed of **different sums** prime magic squares of order 4.

Example 7. Equal Sums Blocks of Order 22. Let's consider following **prime magic square** of order 44:

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 44. It is composed of **equal sums** prime magic squares of order 22. Each block of order 22 is nested with prime magic square of order 20. It is further composed of four **equal sums** concentric prime magic squares of order 10.

Example 9. Equal Sums Blocks of Order 22. Let's consider following **prime magic square** of order 44:

magic squares of order 10.

Example 10. Equal Sums Blocks of Order 22. Let's consider following **prime magic square** of order 44:

1434457	1633039	662713	1660207	978343	1284763	1202317	551269	1166713	971917	326617	429007	1619383	799633	374587	1343197	726163	1362349	951697	534229	1451179	536287	1100857	1054639	479533	696889	1375747	535273	1596697	522199	613993	1642903	859057	1398037	724729	1243717	255649	1062343	994657	1503883	1394299	849049	1209973	885943
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It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 44. It is composed of four **equal sums concentric prime magic squares** of order 22.

*It is **concentric single-layer bordered prime magic square** of order 44. The internal blocks of orders 42 is also a **concentric prime magic square** studied in the previous work [15].*

2.2 Prime Magic Squares of Order 45

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 45 with different representations. We know that $45 = 3^2 \times 5$. It means that most of the blocks are compositions of prime magic squares of orders 3, 5, 9 and 15.

Example 12. Different Sums Blocks of Order 15. *Let's consider following **prime magic square** of order 45:*

2552527	1045819	1859653	850009	657091	955807	1738423	675079	722317	1968163	708823	879493	302857	109141	127843	122443	146539	236407	380713	277789	455557	412987	222841	479023	79873	104773	131113	491251	533857	975379	544171	236107	591559	2622559	1642141	1726567	1611097	1607839	2643073	707653	922321	1669897	4025317	2396887	1849357
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*It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 45. It is composed of **different sums prime magic squares** of order 15. The blocks of order 15 are again composed of **different sums prime magic squares** of order 3.*

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 45. It is composed of **equal sums** prime magic squares of order 15. The blocks of order 15 are again composed of **different sums** prime magic squares of order 3.

Example 14. Different Sums Blocks of Order 15. Let's consider following **prime magic square** of order 45:

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 45. It is composed of **equal sums** prime magic squares of order 15. The blocks of order 15 are again composed of **different sums** concentric prime magic squares of order 5.

Example 16. Different Sums Concentric Blocks of Order 15. Let's consider following **prime magic square** of order 45:

1019281	665857	513691	521281	585643	826411	591457	450223	674767	778963	745933	386713	588151	197161	177823	1168537	1005331	2581669	1652509	2689369	1153891	2916757	485347	1963639	1750669	2317327	1993219	865597	1276027	2366347	202339	446227	727729	615427	386887	875089	633649	210619	1083583	368083	1092493	602317	917593	800077	1128433
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It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 45. It is composed of **different sums concentric prime magic squares** of order 15.

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 45. It is composed of **equal sums** concentric prime magic squares of order 15.

Example 18. Different Sums Blocks of Order 9. Let's consider following **prime magic square** of order 45:

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 45. It is composed of **equal sums** prime magic squares of order 9. The blocks of order 9 are again composed of **different sums** prime magic squares of order 3.

Example 20. Different Sums Concentric Blocks of Order 9. Let's consider following **prime magic square** of order 45:

It is **block-structured prime magic square** of order 45. It is composed of **equal sums** concentric prime magic squares of order 9.

Example 22. Concentric Single-Layer Bordered Prime Magic Square. Let's consider following **prime magic square** of order 45:

2.3 Prime Magic Squares of Order 46

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 46 with different representations. We know that $46 = 2 \times 23$. It means that most of the blocks are compositions of prime magic squares of order 23. Since there is only possibility of block-structured, i.e., 4 times 23, that's why we constructed more prime magic squares of order 46 based on the prime magic squares of order 44 considering an extra border resulting in prime magic squares of order 46. These types of magic squares, we call as **block-bordered**.

Example 23. Block-Bordered Prime Magic Square. *Let's consider following prime magic square of order 46:*

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 46. The internal block of order 44 is composed of **different sums** concentric prime magic squares of order 11.

Example 25. Block-Structured Prime Magic Square. Let's consider following **prime magic square** of order 46:

*It is **concentric single-layer bordered prime magic square** of order 46. The inner block of order 44 is also a **concentric single-layer bordered prime magic square** studied above.*

2.4 Prime Magic Squares of Order 47

Below are few examples of prime magic squares of order 47. Since 47 is a prime number, we don't have factors of 47. In this case, we shall use the blocks of order 45 and create a single-layer border resulting in prime magic square of order 47, These type of magic squares we call as block-bordered prime magic square. Let's see some examples;

Example 27. Block-Bordered Prime Magic Square. *Let's consider following **prime magic square** of order 47:*

It is **block-bordered prime magic square** of order 47, where the internal block of order 45 is composed of **equal sums** concentric prime magic squares of order 9.

Example 32. Concentric Single-Layer Bordered Prime Magic Square. Let's consider following **prime magic square** of order 47:

3 Author's Contribution to Recreation of Numbers and Magic Squares

- (i) **Inder J. Taneja**, Recreation of Numbers - <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=671>.
- (ii) **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Squares - <https://numbers-magic.com/?cat=3>. Also for the publications on magic squares see the link: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=668>.

References

- [1] **H.E. Dudeney**, Amusements in Mathematics, The Authors' Club, 1917.
- [2] **H. Harvey**, Prime Numbers Magic Squares <http://recmath.org/MagicSquares/primesqr.htm>
- [3] **C. Riveira**, The Prime Puzzle and Problem Connections, <https://www.primepuzzles.net/>
- [4] **H. White**, Bordered Magic Squares - <http://budshaw.ca/BorderedMagicSquares.html>
- [5] **H. White**, Magic Squares of Prime Numbers, <https://budshaw.ca/PrimeMagicSquares.html>
- [6] **Makarova, Natalia**, Concentric magic squares of primes, <http://primesmagicgames.altervista.org/wp/forums/topic/concentric-magic-squares-of-primes/>.
Also refers: <http://www.natalimak1.narod.ru/sqmin1.htm>; <http://www.natalimak1.narod.ru/sqmin2.htm>;
<http://www.natalimak1.narod.ru/sqmin3.htm>; <http://www.klassikpoez.narod.ru/glavnaja.htm>.
- [7] **Roberto C. Angelone**, A Fully Nested 729 x 729 Unique-Prime Magic Square Constructed from Nine Correlated 243 x 243 Prime Magic Blocks, <https://zenodo.org/records/20098521>.

• Prime Magic Squares

- [8] **Inder J. Taneja**, Single-Layer Bordered Even and Odd Orders Primes Magic Squares: Orders 120 and 121, **Zenodo**, May June 16, 2026, pp. 1-36, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20723312>.
Web-site links: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19224> and <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19258>.
- [9] **Inder J. Taneja**, Higher Order block-structured prime magic squares: Order 1220 Multiples of 4, **Zenodo**, June 16, 2026, pp. 1-27, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20723328>.
Web-site link: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19291>.

- [10] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-structured prime magic squares: Orders 6 to 14, **Zenodo**, June 16, 2026, pp. 1-41, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20723272>
Web-site link: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19319>.
- [11] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-structured prime magic squares: Orders 15 to 23, **Zenodo**, June 16, 2026, pp. 1-76, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20723291>.
Web-site link: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19410>.
- [12] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-structured prime magic squares: Orders 24, 25 and 26, **Zenodo**, June 18, 2026, pp. 1-26, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20723291>.
Web-site link: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19518>.
- [13] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-structured prime magic squares: Orders 27 to 31, **Zenodo**, June 22, 2026, pp. 1-59, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20791309>.
Web-site link: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19566>.
- [14] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-structured prime magic squares: Orders 32 to 38, **Zenodo**, June 25, 2026, pp. 1-75, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20839802>.
Web-site link: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19641>.
- [15] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-structured prime magic squares: Orders 39 to 43, **Zenodo**, June 28, 2026, pp. 1-61, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20999874>.
Web-site link: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19723>.
- [16] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-structured prime magic squares of Orders 44 to 47, extbfZenodo, July 01, 2026, pp. 1-59, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21109199>.
Web-site link: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19786>.
- [17] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-structured prime magic squares of Orders 48 to 51, In preparation
Web-site link: <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=19824>.
- [18] **Inder J. Taneja**, Higher Order Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares Multiples of 3, 5 and 7, In Preparation.
- [19] **Inder J. Taneja**, Higher Order Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares Multiples of 4, 6 and 8, In Preparation.
- [20] **Inder J. Taneja**, Higher Order Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares Multiples 9, 11 and 13, In Preparation.
- [21] **Inder J. Taneja**, Higher Order Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares Multiples 10, 12 and 14, In Preparation.
- [22] **Inder J. Taneja**, Higher Order Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares Multiples 15, 17 and 19, In Preparation.
- [23] **Inder J. Taneja**, Higher Order Block-Structured Prime Magic Squares Multiples 16, 18 and 20, In Preparation.

• Block-Wise Magic Squares

- [24] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Constructions of Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 8 to 108, May 15, 2019, pp. 1-43, **Zenodo**, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2843326>.
- [25] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Equal Sums Pandiagonal Magic Squares of Order $4k$, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-17, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554288>.
- [26] **Inder J. Taneja**, Magic Rectangles in Construction of Block-Wise Pandiagonal Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, January 31, 2019, pp. 1-49, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554520>.
- [27] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Equal Sums Magic Squares of Orders $3k$ and $6k$, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-55, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2554895>.
- [28] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Unequal Sums Magic Squares, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-52, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555260>.
- [29] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 12 to 36, **Zenodo**, February 1, 2019, pp. 1-53, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555343>.
- [30] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 39 to 45, **Zenodo**, February 2, 2019, pp. 1-73, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2555889>.
- [31] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Wise and Block-Bordered Magic and Bimagic Squares of Orders 10 to 47. **Zenodo**, January 14, 2021, pp. 1-185, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4437783>.
- [32] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered and Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares: Odd Order Multiples, **Zenodo**, February 10, 2021, pp. 1-75, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4527739>
- [33] **Inder J. Taneja**, Bordered and Block-Wise Bordered Magic Squares: Even Order Multiples, **Zenodo**, February 10, 2021, pp. 1-96, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4527746>

• Block-Bordered Magic Squares

- [34] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - I, **Zenodo**, August 18, 2020, pp. 1-81, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3990291>.
- [35] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - II, **Zenodo**, August 18, 2020, pp. 1-90, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3990293>.
- [36] **Inder J. Taneja**, Block-Bordered Magic Squares of Prime and Double Prime Numbers - III, **Zenodo**, September 01, 2020, pp. 1-93, <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4011213>.

• Double-Digit Bordered Magic Squares

- [37] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares Multiples of 4: Orders 8 to 24, **Zenodo**, April, 26, 2023, pp. 1-43, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7866956>.

- [38] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 28 and 32, **Zenodo**, April, 26, 2023, pp. 1-36, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7866981>.
- [39] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 10, 14, 18 and 22, **Zenodo**, April, 30, 2023, pp. 1-43, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7880931>.
- [40] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 26 and 30, **Zenodo**, April, 30, 2023, pp. 1-45, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7880937>.
- [41] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 36 and 40, **Zenodo**, May, 04, 2023, pp. 1-41, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7896709>.
- [42] **Inder J. Taneja**, Two digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 34 and 38, **Zenodo**, May 10, 2023, pp. 1-45, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7922571>.
- [43] **Inder J. Taneja**, New Concepts in Magic Squares: Double Digits Bordered Magic Squares of Orders 7 to 108, **Zenodo**, August 09, 2023, pp. 1-30, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8230214>.

• Cornered Magic Squares

- [44] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares of Order 6, **Zenodo**, May 23, 2023, pp. 1-23, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7960679>.
- [45] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 5 to 13, **Zenodo**, June 03, 2023, pp. 1-71, <https://10.5281/zenodo.8000467>.
- [46] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 14 to 24, **Zenodo**, June 03, 2023, pp. 1-39, <https://10.5281/zenodo.8000471>.
- [47] **Inder J. Taneja**, New Concepts in Magic Squares: Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 5 to 81, **Zenodo**, August 09, 2023, pp. 1-27, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8231157>.
- [48] **Inder J. Taneja**, Cornered Magic Squares in Construction of Magic Squares of Orders 16, 20, 24 and 28, **Zenodo**, August 23, 2023, <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=10172>.
- [49] **Inder J. Taneja**, Striped and Semi-Striped Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 6 to 50, <https://numbers-magic.com/?p=15048>, March 17, 2025
- [50] **Inder J. Taneja**, New Concepts in Magic Squares: Cornered Magic Squares of Orders 5 to 108, **Zenodo**, January 29, 2025, pp. 1-33, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14759238>.